

Effective Pedagogical Strategies for Teaching English Language to Civil Servants

Phyu Phyu Aung

phyuphyuaung.sstars@gmail.com

Civil Service Academy (Upper Myanmar)

Abstract

Teaching English language to civil servants appears many opportunities for trainers. In the meantime, it poses unique challenges for them due to the diverse backgrounds, varying levels of expertise and practical necessity of English language fluency of the trainees, and large class, time constraint, and no enough human resources of the training course. This paper finds out the realm of effective pedagogical strategies suitable for these unique needs and challenges of teaching English language to civil servants. Effective pedagogical strategies of English language teaching play a vital role for educators to bridge the language gap, to empower civil servants, and to ultimately contribute to more proficient and effective governance in multicultural contexts. In the real world, there are many effective teaching strategies and methods, however, some suitable strategies and methods during the very short period of teaching English language are highly expressed in this paper. This paper also highlights practical strategies based on the competencies which the trainers must have to effectively manage, assess and facilitate learning in large class of civil servant trainees with the aim of creating a healthy and happy learning environment for civil servants.

Keywords: *pedagogical strategies, teaching English language, large class, civil servants training course, healthy learning environment*

1. INTRODUCTION

English language proficiency stands as a paramount requirement for civil servants, serving as a linchpin for effective communication in international relations and collaborations. The imperative for fluency emerges from the frequent interactions civil servants have with foreign dignitaries and stakeholders, wherein English serves as the lingua franca. In an era characterized by globalization, proficiency in English becomes indispensable for civil servants to engage meaningfully with global partners and navigate the complexities of international affairs. However, the task of imparting English language skills to civil servants presents a multifaceted challenge, stemming from their diverse backgrounds, varying levels of proficiency, and the practical necessity of fluency in English.

Pedagogy, denoting the methodology and approach employed by instructors in teaching and learning, has traditionally been associated with face-to-face classroom environments. Nevertheless, the evolution of pedagogical practices has extended beyond traditional settings to encompass online, hybrid, and blended learning modalities. While the principles of effective pedagogy remain consistent across these modalities, educators must adapt their strategies to suit the unique demands of each environment.

Effective pedagogical strategies in English language teaching play a pivotal role in bridging linguistic barriers, empowering civil servants, and fostering proficient and effective governance in multicultural contexts. By implementing systematic approaches tailored to the

diverse needs of learners, educators can equip civil servants with the language skills necessary for success in an increasingly interconnected world.

2. **BACKGROUND**

The best language educators can often be identified by their commitment to creative and innovative classroom teaching strategies. They're constantly trying new language teaching strategies to engage their students and experimenting with new language learning activities and teaching tools to improve learning outcomes.

2.1 **Difference between teaching strategy and teaching method**

Teaching strategy encompasses the broader plan or framework designed by an educator to achieve specific learning outcomes and goals whereas teaching methods are the specific techniques or procedures used by teachers to deliver lessons, impart information, and facilitate learning within the framework of a teaching strategy. Thus, teaching strategy and teaching method are related concepts in education although they have distinct differences.

Each teaching method has its own advantages and challenges, and the effectiveness of each depends on various factors such as the learning objectives, context, and learner characteristics. These teaching methods can be employed individually or in combination to create dynamic and effective learning environments adaptable to the needs of diverse learners.

Customizing language content & offering differentiated instructions: It means adapting the content and instruction to meet the individual needs and abilities of learners. As the pros, differentiated instruction meets individual learner needs, accommodates diverse learning styles and preferences, promotes personalized learning experiences, As the cons, it requires significant planning and preparation, time-consuming to create customized content for each learner, potential for unequal treatment if not implemented effectively.

Leveled tasks: Leveled tasks mean assigning tasks or activities at different difficulty levels based on the learners' proficiency levels. For the pros, it allows for differentiation based on learners' proficiency levels, provides appropriate challenges for each learner, and helps maintain engagement by matching tasks to learners' abilities. For the cons, it requires accurate assessment of learners' proficiency levels, may lead to labeling or stigmatization of learners at lower levels and requires careful monitoring to ensure tasks are appropriately leveled.

Discussions: Discussion means engaging learners in verbal exchanges to explore topics, share ideas, and develop critical thinking skills. Its pros are: encouraging critical thinking and analysis; fostering communication and collaboration skills; and providing opportunities for peer learning and sharing perspectives whereas the cons include that it can be dominated by more vocal participants; it requires skilled facilitation to ensure all voices are heard; and it may veer off-topic without proper guidance.

Case studies: Case studies are “presenting real-life scenarios for analysis and problem-solving, often used to apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations”. It has the pros that applies theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios, encourages problem-solving and decision-making skills, and promotes deeper understanding

through practical application and the cons of that availability of relevant case studies may be limited, that can be time-consuming to analyze and discuss in depth, and it may not fully replicate real-world complexities.

Role plays: Role plays mean assigning specific roles to learners to simulate real-life interactions or situations, fostering communication and empathy. The pros of role plays are: to provide opportunities for experiential learning, to enhance communication and interpersonal skills and to encourage empathy and perspective-taking meanwhile its cons are to require a supportive and non-judgmental environment, to some learners may feel uncomfortable or self-conscious, and to lack authenticity if scenarios are not well-designed.

Self-paced learning materials: Self-paced learning materials means providing resources that allow learners to progress at their own speed, accommodating individual learning styles and preferences. Its pros are that it accommodates individual learning styles and paces, promotes autonomy and self-regulation, and allows for flexibility in scheduling and progress tracking. Moreover, its cons are that it requires motivated and disciplined learners, it may lead to feelings of isolation without sufficient interaction, and limited opportunity for immediate feedback or clarification.

Group work: Collaborative activities where learners work together to achieve common goals, promoting teamwork and interpersonal skills are called group work. The pros include encouraging collaboration and teamwork, fostering communication and interpersonal skills and providing diverse perspectives and peer learning opportunities. The cons include potential for unequal participation or free-riding, requiring effective group dynamics and conflict resolution skills and that it may result in slower progress if groups encounter difficulties.

Peer tutoring: It means pairing learners to support and teach each other, enhancing understanding through peer interaction. The pros are that it encourages active learning and engagement, builds confidence and communication skills and reinforces understanding through teaching others. The cons are that it requires training and support for peer tutors, may perpetuate misunderstandings if tutors are not knowledgeable and potential for peer dynamics to affect learning outcomes.

Pair mentoring: Pair mentoring means matching learners with more experienced individuals for guidance and support in achieving learning objectives. Its pros are that it provides personalized support and guidance, builds rapport and trust between mentor and mentee and offers opportunities for mutual learning and growth. Its cons are that it requires matching mentors and mentees effectively, time and resource-intensive to provide ongoing mentoring and potential for unequal relationships or power dynamics.

Technology: Technology means utilizing digital tools and platforms to enhance teaching and learning experiences, such as educational software, apps, and multimedia resources. It has the pros of enhancing access to resources and information, facilitating interactive and multimedia learning experiences, and supporting individualized instruction and personalized feedback while it has the cons

of requiring infrastructure and technical support, being distracting or overwhelming if not used purposefully and exacerbating inequalities in access and digital literacy skills.

Flipped classroom: Flipped classroom means reversing the traditional lecture and homework elements of a lesson, with instructional content delivered outside of class and in-class time used for application and discussion. Its pros are to promote active learning and student engagement, to maximize class time for interactive activities and discussions, to provide flexibility for students to review content at their own pace. But its cons are to require careful planning and preparation of pre-class materials, to rely on students' self-discipline and motivation to engage with materials outside of class, and not to be suitable for all subjects or learning objectives.

Short task-based learning: Short task-based learning means structuring learning activities around specific tasks or objectives, focusing on practical application and skill development. The pros of this method are: fostering problem-solving and critical thinking skills; promoting active learning and engagement; allowing for quick feedback; and assessment of understanding. The cons are: lacking depth or breadth compared to longer learning activities; requiring careful selection; and design of tasks to ensure relevance and effectiveness; not addressing complex or multifaceted learning objectives.

Intensive language practice: Intensive language practice means providing concentrated and focused opportunities for learners to practice language skills, often through drills, exercises, or immersive experiences. Its pros include: accelerating language acquisition through focused practice; building fluency and confidence in language use; providing immediate feedback and correction while its cons include: being repetitive and monotonous without variety; leading to learner fatigue or burnout if overly intensive; requiring balance with other language learning activities to develop comprehensive skills.

Digital resources: Digital resources mean utilizing digital content such as e-books, online articles, videos, and interactive exercises to support learning objectives. Its pros are: that it enhances access to a wide range of educational materials; facilitates interactive and multimedia learning experiences; and supports individualized and self-directed learning. Moreover, its cons are: that quality and reliability of digital resources can vary; it requires digital literacy skills and access to technology; it may not fully replace traditional learning materials or experiences.

Peer interaction: Peer interaction means encouraging learners to engage with their peers through discussions, collaborative projects, and shared learning experiences. The pros of this method are: that it encourages collaboration and teamwork; fosters social and emotional development; and it provides opportunities for peer learning and support. The cons are: that it can be influenced by peer dynamics or social pressures; it may lead to distractions or off-task behavior; and it requires guidance and supervision to ensure productive interactions.

Learner-centered method: It means placing the learner at the center of the instructional process, focusing on their needs, interests, and goals. Its pros include:

empowering learners to take ownership of their learning; promoting intrinsic motivation and self-directed learning skills; and adapting instruction to individual needs, interests, and preferences when its cons include: requiring a shift in teaching roles and approaches; challenging to implement in traditional educational settings; and requiring ongoing support and encouragement for learner autonomy.

Small-group projects: Small-group projects means assigning tasks or projects to small groups of learners to encourage cooperation, communication, and problem-solving skills. It has the pros of encouraging collaboration, communication, and teamwork, fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills, providing opportunities for creativity and innovation while its cons are: requiring effective group management and coordination; leading to unequal participation or conflicts within groups; and that evaluation and grading can be challenging, especially for individual contributions.

2.2 The Southeast Asia Teachers' Competency Framework

The Southeast Asia competency framework for teachers offers a refreshingly holistic perspective for teachers. Becoming a better teacher every day is an aspiration that all Southeast Asian teachers can proudly embrace.

Know and Understand What I Teach: Knowing and understanding what to teach is the ability of teachers to deepen and broaden their knowledge on what to teach, understand education trends, policies, and curricula and be updated on local, national, regional, and global developments. At the core of the teacher competency framework is the belief that effective teaching involves knowing and understanding what one teaches, from deepening and broadening knowledge on subjects taught, to staying up to date with education trends, policies, and curricula. An awareness of local, national, regional, and global developments is also essential for teachers to properly respond to changes within their classroom environment.

Help My Students Learn: Helping students learn is the ability to know their students, use the most effective teaching and learning strategy and assess and give feedback on how students learn. Educators need to keep the objectives of providing meaningful feedback about how they are learning and what areas need improvement in mind when planning their lessons and creating assessments or activities; not just teaching for the sake of teaching, but rather personalizing instruction based on individual student needs.

Engage the Community: Engaging the community is the ability to partner with parents and caregivers, involve the community to help students learn, and encourage respect and diversity. The teachers' competency framework seeks to foster mutual respect and understanding by helping people find common ground in shared experiences. Through this framework, educators are empowered to create meaningful relationships with families through effective sharing of information, establishment of clear communication within the educational environment, and mutual participation in activities at the school level. The goal is for teachers to create a safe and supportive learning environment that encourages students to be their best selves and allows everyone involved to have their voices heard.

Becoming a better teacher every day: Becoming a better teacher every day, teacher should have the ability to know one-self and others, practice human goodness. and then master the teaching practice. All these competencies make up a strong foundation for teachers who want to offer a quality education experience to their pupils in Southeast Asia and help foster joyful learners. The competency framework for teachers in Southeast Asia provides educators with an invaluable resource for understanding the skills and knowledge needed to cultivate classroom environments in line with 21st century learning concepts.

Figure: The Southeast Asia Teachers' Competency Framework Model

3. IMPLEMENTATION

Within the Civil Service Academy, a spectrum of eight regular training courses caters to civil service personnel across various ministries and organizations, spanning from Executive Level Officials to Clerical Staff. While English language texts have been specified for executive and senior level courses, a generalized curriculum prevails for the remaining courses, including those targeting mid-level officials to clerical staff, which serve as the focal point of this study. These courses, characterized by their brevity, typically last no more than two weeks and contend with class sizes exceeding 100 trainees. The prevalent challenges encompassing generalized curricula, diverse trainee backgrounds, time constraints, large class sizes, and staffing shortages confront virtually all courses aimed at teaching English language

to civil servants. Addressing these challenges, this paper elucidates effective pedagogical strategies grounded in the Southeast Asia Teachers Competency Framework. These strategies encompass “know and understand what to teach”, “help the trainees learn”, “engage the organization”, “manage the classroom well” and “become a better trainer every day”. Additionally, recognizing the distinctive challenge posed by large class sizes, an additional strategy tailored to this context is introduced.

3.1 Know and understand what to teach

The design and implementation of course curricula across various ministries and organizations often lack specificity, necessitating a proactive approach from trainers to tailor content to the specific needs of their trainees. To achieve this,

- (1) Trainers must first familiarize themselves with prevailing education trends and existing curricula.
- (2) Subsequently, conducting a thorough needs assessment, even if constrained by time limitations, through informal interviews becomes imperative to discern the precise English language requirements within the trainees' respective workplaces.
- (3) With insights gathered, trainers can then meticulously determine subject content and its sequencing, ensuring alignment with the English proficiency levels of the trainees.
- (4) Crafting a detailed lesson plan that accommodates time constraints is paramount, further necessitating integration of updated local, national, regional, and global developments to enrich the learning experience.

By adhering to these strategies, trainers can effectively optimize the relevance and efficacy of their course delivery, thereby enhancing the learning outcomes for their trainees.

3.2 Help the trainees learn

In Civil Service Academy (CSA), trainees are destined for diverse roles across various ministries or organizations, each possessing unique backgrounds and workplace experiences. To effectively address this heterogeneity,

- (1) Trainers must employ pedagogically sound teaching and learning methodologies.
- (2) Customization of language content and delivery becomes paramount, necessitating the utilization of differentiated instructions such as leveled tasks, discussions, case studies, role-plays, self-paced learning materials, group work, peer tutoring, and pair mentoring.
- (3) While the implementation of teaching methods and activities may vary based on the trainers' creativity, continual assessment and feedback mechanisms are indispensable.
- (4) Regular formative assessments, both pre- and post-tests, conducted on individual and group learning, enable trainers to gauge progress and provide timely and constructive feedback.

- (5) Additionally, soliciting feedback from trainees following each training session or subject ensures alignment with their evolving needs and preferences, thereby fostering a collaborative and adaptive learning environment.

3.3 Engage the organization

In CSA, training courses are inherently short-term, typically spanning approximately two weeks. Given this limited timeframe, the efficacy of English language instruction hinges upon active engagement from both the training academy and the trainees' respective ministries. Trainers face the challenge of delivering impactful and practical language skills within constrained timeframes, necessitating a strategic approach.

- (1) Leveraging technology, adopting a flipped classroom model, employing short task-based learning methods, and facilitating intensive language practice sessions are essential strategies to optimize learning outcomes.
- (2) Furthermore, trainers must encourage trainees to seamlessly integrate and apply newfound language skills within their workplace contexts.
- (3) Concurrently, organizations must create opportunities for trainees to utilize English language skills in practical settings, fostering a conducive environment for experiential learning.

Through this symbiotic approach, trainees acquire invaluable practical experiences, perpetuating a cycle of continuous learning and skill enhancement.

3.4 Manage the classroom well

In the operational context, trainers are confronted with the formidable task of managing large class sizes, often exceeding 100 trainees per session. To effectively navigate this challenge, trainers must possess adept classroom management skills.

- (1) Primarily, this entails the implementation of group and rotation-based activities, alongside the integration of digital resources, flipped classroom methodologies, and peer interactions.
- (2) Within the expansive class setting, trainers assume multifaceted roles as facilitators of activities, managers of group dynamics, timekeepers, and instructional designers simultaneously.
- (3) Moreover, in facilitating the use of digital resources and flipped classroom approaches, trainers serve as guides in navigating technology and maintaining efficient time management.
- (4) Furthermore, when fostering peer interaction among trainees, trainers play a pivotal role in assessing interactions and providing constructive feedback.
- (5) Through adept management and strategic facilitation, trainers can optimize the learning experience within large class environments, ensuring meaningful engagement and effective knowledge transfer for all participants.

3.5 Become a better trainer everyday

In response to the challenge of limited human resources, trainers must continuously strive to enhance their skills and effectiveness. This entails not only mastering optimal teaching methodologies but also accumulating diverse teaching experiences over time. Given

the scarcity of trainers, each individual faces a substantial workload in delivering lectures within their schedules. To alleviate this burden and foster professional development,

- (1) Trainers should promote self-directed learning, peer collaboration, learner-centered approaches, small-group projects, and the integration of digital resources and flipped classroom techniques.
- (2) Additionally, facilitating feedback sessions among co-trainers, sharing best practices, and actively seeking opportunities to gain practical experience in real-life scenarios are essential strategies.
- (3) By embracing a culture of continuous learning and collaboration, trainers can adapt to resource constraints while maintaining high standards of training delivery and professional growth.

4. EVALUATION AND RECOMMENDATION

Utilizing appropriate and effective pedagogical strategies in English language instruction fosters active engagement among trainees, facilitating seamless comprehension and eliminating barriers to learning. This active involvement not only cultivates a positive and vibrant learning atmosphere for civil servants but also instills a sense of joy and enthusiasm for learning. Furthermore, it encourages the practical application of language and communication skills in real-world contexts. By adhering to the principles outlined in the Southeast Asia Teachers Competency Framework (SEA-TCF), trainers can introduce innovative teaching methodologies into their classrooms. The successful implementation of these strategies empowers educators to create dynamic learning environments and reinforces their commitment to delivering the highest quality educational experiences.

Furthermore, trainers can streamline their focus on specific language skills pertinent to civil service roles, such as basic communication, essential vocabulary, and common workplace phrases, within the limited two-week training period. To tackle various challenges, trainers must exhibit creativity in selecting suitable methods and activities tailored to the trainees' needs. Additionally, trainers should possess a nuanced understanding of the advantages and disadvantages associated with different teaching methodologies, complemented by a proficient level of English language proficiency themselves. Emphasizing the importance of ongoing practice and language exposure beyond the training duration is crucial for sustained skill development. Implementing pre-tests, mid-tests, and post-tests aid in gauging trainee progress effectively. While the segmentation of classes based on English proficiency levels, when feasible, enhances learning outcomes. Regular feedback collection, conducted after each session or trainer interaction, enables trainers to promptly address trainee needs and adapt teaching methods accordingly. Continuous review and revision of the curriculum, teaching strategies, and methods ensure the integration of modernized approaches alongside traditional techniques. To support lifelong learning and sustainable language development, resources for post-training learning and practice should be readily available, supplemented by opportunities for local and overseas training initiatives for trainers.

5. CONCLUSION

The effective pedagogical strategies employed in teaching English language to civil servants necessitate a holistic approach, acknowledging the diverse backgrounds, needs, and

professional contexts of adult learners. Through the integration of varied methodologies and techniques, educators can foster a dynamic learning environment that promotes language acquisition and proficiency enhancement. Mastery of these strategies equips trainers to facilitate effective communication, collaboration, and access to global information among civil servants. By intertwining language instruction with other skill development initiatives, such as leadership training or technical competencies, a more adept and capable civil service workforce can be cultivated. Ultimately, bolstering language proficiency among civil servants not only enhances individual capacities but also contributes significantly to the advancement of good governance practices.

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REFERENCES

1. Ahmar Mahboob and Angel M. Y. Lin, “Pedagogical strategies for teaching English as an International Language in the context of globalization”.
2. G. Verplaetse and S. Leuven, “The Impact of Pedagogical Strategies on Learners' Interactional Performance”.
3. H. Douglas Brown, “Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy”.
4. Jack C. Richards and Theodore S. Rodgers (2014), “Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching”.
5. Jim Scrivener, “Learning Teaching: The Essential Guide to English Language Teaching”.
6. Lin, O., Arumugam, N., Mohamad, F., Suppiah, P. C., & Lwin, A. S. (2021), “Needs Analysis on the Importance of English Communication Skills for Government Officials in Myanmar. International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences”, 11(3), 612-624.
7. Southeast Asia Teachers Competency Framework (SEA-TCF), 2018

Internet Sources

1. <https://myteflsolutions.com/english-learning-approaches-methods/>
2. <https://sanako.com/the-10-best-language-teaching-strategies-explained>
3. <https://www.montclair.edu/itds/digital-pedagogy/pedagogical-strategies-and-practices/>